

Machine learning discoveries of TIMELESS-X synergy in ETC-1922159 treated colorectal cancer cells

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Abstract

TIMELESS plays a role in the circadian rhythm of *Drosophila*, however in mammalian biology it is known to play its role as DNA replication fork component, promoter of fork progression and participator in cell cycle checkpoint signaling in response to DNA damage. In colorectal cancer (CRC) cells treated with ETC-1922159, TIMELESS was found to be down regulated along with other genes. A recently developed search engine ranked combinations of TIMELESS-X (X, a particular gene/protein) at 2nd order level after drug administration. Some of these combinations have been tested in wet lab, however many have been pointed out by the search engine that are yet to be explored/tested. These rankings reveal which TIMELESS-X combinations might be working synergistically in CRC. In this research work, I cover combinations of TIMELESS with members of ataxia telangiectasia mutated (ATM), ataxia telangiectasia and Rad3 related (ATR), matrix metalloproteinase (MMP), v-myc avian myelocytomatosis viral oncogene homolog (MYC), myosin (MYO), transcription termination factor (TTF), sirtuin (SIRT), TIMELESS interacting protein (TIPIN), UBX domain protein (UBXN), DEAD/H (Asp-Glu-Ala-Asp/His) box helicase (DDX), DNA polymerase (POL), DNA-dependent RNA polymerase (POLR), minichromosome maintenance complex (MCM), go-ichi-ni-san (GINS), F-box (FBX), ring finger protein (RNF), H2A histone family member (H2A), high mobility group (HMG), Wnt family member (WNT), microRNA non-coding host genes (MIR-x-HG), Forkhead box (FOX), poly(ADP-ribose) polymerase (PARP) and phosphodiesterase (PDE) family.

Keywords: TIMELESS, Porcupine inhibitor ETC-1922159, Sensitivity analysis, Machine learning, Colorectal cancer.

^{*}ML discoveries of TIMELESS-X synergy in ETC-1922159 treated CRC cells

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1. Introduction

1.1. TIMELESS

A circadian rhythm is a natural oscillation that repeats roughly every 24 hours and can refer to any process that originates within an organism and responds to the environment. They are regulated by a circadian clock, the primary function which is to co-ordinate biological processes so they occur at the correct time to maximize the fitness of an individual. Circadian rhythm consists of light/dark phases which coincide with the phases of the solar day.

TIMELESS (TIM) is a gene in multiple species but widely known in *Drosophila* (dTIM) for regulating circadian rhythm, first reported by Sehgal et al. [1]. The mammalian TIM (mTIM) was identified by Gotter et al. [2] in mouse as a potential circadian clock component, however its role in clock regulation has been more controversial (Gotter [3]). Gotter et al. [2] show that mTIM is essential for embryonic development, but does not have substantiated circadian function. mTIM has now been characterized as a DNA replication fork component and has been shown to promote fork progression and participate in cell cycle checkpoint signaling in response to DNA damage (Cai and Chiu [4]). Cell cycle checkpoints ensure completion of biochemical reactions unique to G1, S, G2, and M in phase of proliferating mammalian cells, prior to emergence of subsequent phases.

Gotter et al. [5] demonstrate that mTIM and its constitutive binding partner, TIM-interacting protein (TIPIN), are replisome-associated proteins, which associate with components of the endogenous replication fork complex, and are present at BrdU-positive DNA replication sites. Further, Cho et al. [6] show that mTIM and TIM-interacting protein (TIPIN) complex couple replicative DNA helicase CMG (CDC45, MCM2-7, GINS) and stimulate the activities of DNA polymerase (POL) α , δ , and ϵ , in progressing the replication fork. mTIM is essential for ATR-dependent CHK1 activation and S-phase arrest (Yang et al. [7]). ATR and ataxia telangiectasia mutated (ATM) work at the heart of sensing DNA damage and phosphorylate checkpoint kinase 1/2 (CHK1/2), as observed by Blackford and Jackson [8]. In response to DNA damage and efficient homologous recombination repair, Xie et al. [9] show that mTIM physically interacts with and recruits poly [ADP-ribose] polymerase 1 (PARP1), independent of poly(ADP-ribosylation), to damaged sites.

Rao and Lin [10] review that abnormal expression of certain clock genes has been found in patients with colorectal cancer (CRC) and their correlation with clinicopathological features has also been explored. In CRC cells treated with ETC-1922159, TIMELESS was found to be down regulated along with other genes. Some combinations of TIMELESS have been confirmed in wet lab, however, many of the combinations have not been explored/tested or are known. To reveal these combinations, I use a modification of a recently published machine learning based search engine, details of which are given in the next section.

1.2. Combinatorial search problem and a possible solution

In a recently published work Sinha [11], a frame work of a search engine was developed which can rank combinations of factors (genes/proteins) in a signaling pathway. Readers are requested to go through the adaptation of the above mentioned work for gaining deeper insight into the working of the pipeline and its use of published data set generated after administration of ETC-1922159, Sinha [12]. The work uses SVM package by Joachims [13] in https://www.cs.cornell.edu/people/tj/svm_light/svm_rank.html. I use the adaptation to rank 2^{nd} order gene combinations.

2. Results & Discussion

2.1. TIMELESS related synergies

2.1.1. TIMELESS - Individual members

mTIM is essential for ATR-dependent CHK1 activation and S-phase arrest and Yang et al. [7] report that TIM is likewise essential for ATM-dependent CHK2-mediated signaling of doxorubicin-induced DNA double strand breaks. Further, they show that TIM depletion attenuates doxorubicin-induced G2/M cell cycle arrest and sensitizes cancer cells to doxorubicin-induced cytotoxicity. ATR and ataxia telangiectasia mutated (ATM) work at the heart of sensing DNA damage and phosphorylate checkpoint kinase 1/2 (CHK1/2), as observed by Blackford and Jackson [8]. Liu et al. [14] found that the hippocampal MMP9 expression was correlated with the expression levels of circadian genes PER2, PER3, TIMELESS, FBXL3, and NFIL3. PER2 and TIMELESS were upregulated in mouse hippocampus after sleep deprivation (SD). Chi et al. [15] found that overexpression of TIM dramatically enhanced, while knockdown of TIM suppressed the self-renewal of cancer stem cells (CSCs), cell invasion and migration abilities of breast cancer cells in vitro. Their mechanism studies revealed that TIM upregulated the expression and activity of MYC. In CRC tissues, Cao et al. [16] found that TIMELESS was upregulated and mechanistic investigations showed that it activated the β -catenin pathway by binding to Myosin-9 (MYO9). During S phase, the replication and transcription of genomic DNA need to accommodate each other, otherwise their machineries might collide leading to chromosomal instability. Akamatsu and Kobayashi [17] characterized the human replication fork barrier (RFB) that is present downstream from the 47S pre-rRNA gene (ribosomal DNA [rDNA]). They found that the most proximal transcription terminator, SAL box T1, acts as a polar RFB, while the other, SAL box T4/T5, arrests replication forks bidirectionally. The fork-arresting activity at these sites depends on polymerase I (Pol I) transcription termination factor 1 (TTF1) and TIMELESS. In oral squamous cell carcinoma (OSCC), Chen et al. [18] found elevated expression of TIMELESS which enhanced cell proliferation, increased glycolytic activity (glucose uptake and lactate production), and suppressed oxidative phosphorylation (evidenced by reduced oxygen consumption and altered pH levels). SIRT1 was positively associated with TIMELESS expression and expression of SIRT1 increased with the overexpression of TIMELESS levels and decreased with the knockdown of TIMELESS. Gotter et al. [5] demonstrate that mTIM and TIPIN

are replisome-associated proteins. Both proteins associate with components of the endogenous replication fork complex, and are present at BrdU-positive DNA replication sites. A direct binding of the TIM-TIPIN complex to the 34 kDa subunit of replication protein A provides a biochemical explanation for the potential coupling role of these proteins. The eukaryotic replisome is rapidly disassembled during DNA replication termination. In metazoa, the cullin-RING ubiquitin ligase CUL-2LRR-1 drives ubiquitylation of the CMG helicase, leading to replisome disassembly by the p97/CDC-48 "unfoldase". Xia et al. [19] show that the TIMELESS-TIPIN complex is required for CUL-2LRR-1 recruitment and CMG helicase ubiquitylation. Aided by this complex, CUL-2LRR-1 directs ubiquitylation enzymes to ubiquitylate the MCM7 subunit of CMG. Subsequently, the UBXLN3 directly stimulates the disassembly of ubiquitylated CMG by CDC-48_UFD-1_NPL-4. These experimental studies confirm the existence of synergy between the above involved factors with TIMELESS. In colorectal cancer cells treated with ETC-1922159, these individual members, and TIMELESS, were found to be down regulated and their regulation was recorded independently. I was able to rank 2nd order combination of these individual members along with TIMELESS.

Table 1 shows rankings of these combinations. Followed by this is the unexplored combinatorial hypotheses in table 2 generated from analysis of the ranks in table 1. The table 1 shows rankings of these individual members w.r.t TIMELESS. ATR - TIMELESS shows low ranking of 1390 (laplace) and 890 (rbf). ATRIP - TIMELESS shows low ranking of 7 (linear) and 1429 (rbf). MMP11 - TIMELESS shows low ranking of 591 (laplace) and 581 (rbf). MYO19 - TIMELESS shows low ranking of 1359 (laplace) and 648 (linear). TIPIN - TIMELESS shows low ranking of 368 (laplace), 491 (linear) and 436 (rbf). UBXLN8 - TIMELESS shows low ranking of 885 (laplace) and 1361 (rbf). These rankings point to the synergy existing between the two components, which have been down regulated after the drug treatment.

Further, ATM, MYC, TTF2 and SIRT3 showed high ranking and might not be synergistically working with TIMELESS, before treatment.

One can also interpret the results of the table 1 graphically, with the following influences - • individual members w.r.t TIMELESS with TIMELESS – > ATR / ATRIP / MMP11 / MYO19 / TIPIN / UBXLN8.

2.1.2. TIMELESS - DDX

Lerner et al. [20] found that TIMELESS contributes to the ability of the replisome to sense replication-hindering G-quadruplex (G4) formation and ensures resolution of these structures by DDX11 to maintain processive DNA synthesis. These experimental studies confirm the existence of synergy between the above involved factors with TIMELESS. In colorectal cancer cells treated with ETC-1922159, these DDX members, and TIMELESS, were found to be down regulated and their regulation was recorded independently. I was able to rank 2nd order combination of these DDX members along with TIMELESS.

Table 3 shows rankings of these combinations. Followed by this is the unexplored combinatorial hypotheses in table 4 generated from analysis of the ranks in table 3. The table 3 shows rankings of DDX members w.r.t TIMELESS. DDX12P - TIMELESS shows low ranking of 131 (laplace) and 8 (rbf). DDX28 - TIMELESS shows

RANKING INDIVIDUAL MEMBERS VS TIMELESS			
RANKING OF INDIVIDUAL MEMBERS W.R.T TIMELESS			
	laplace	linear	rbf
ATM - TIMELESS	1183	2721	1705
ATR - TIMELESS	1390	2352	890
ATRIP - TIMELESS	2278	7	1429
MMP11 - TIMELESS	591	2682	581
MYC - TIMELESS	1886	1392	2336
MYO19 - TIMELESS	1359	648	2092
TTF2 - TIMELESS	1930	2393	1729
SIRT3 - TIMELESS	1080	1709	2189
TIPIN - TIMELESS	368	491	436
UBXN8 - TIMELESS	885	2478	1361

Table 1: 2nd order interaction ranking between TIMELESS VS Individual members.

UNEXPLORED COMBINATORIAL HYPOTHESES	
Individual members w.r.t TIMELESS	
ATR	TIMELESS
ATRIP	TIMELESS
MMP11	TIMELESS
MYO19	TIMELESS
TIPIN	TIMELESS
UBXN8	TIMELESS

Table 2: 2nd order combinatorial hypotheses between TIMELESS and individual members.

low ranking of 386 (laplace) and 408 (rbf). DDX18 - TIMELESS shows low ranking of 492 (laplace) and 1265 (rbf). DDX11 - TIMELESS shows low ranking of 605 (laplace), 1452 (linear) and 653 (rbf). DDX27 - TIMELESS shows low ranking of 705 (laplace), 843 (linear) and 2279 DDX51 - TIMELESS shows low ranking of 963 (laplace) and 545 (rbf). DDX20 - TIMELESS shows low ranking of 1314 (laplace) and 756 (rbf). DDX55 - TIMELESS shows low ranking of 1438 (laplace) and 746 (rbf). These rankings point to the synergy existing between the two components, which have

been down regulated after the drug treatment.

Further, DDX54, DDX19A, DDX10, DDX21, DDX31, DDX46 and DDX56 showed high ranking and might not be synergistically working with TIMELESS, before treatment.

RANKING DDX MEMBERS VS TIMELESS								
RANKING OF DDX MEMBERS W.R.T TIMELESS								
	laplace	linear	rbf		laplace	linear	rbf	
DDX12P - TIMELESS	131	2039	8	DDX28 - TIMELESS	386	2297	408	
DDX18 - TIMELESS	492	1610	1265	DDX11 - TIMELESS	605	1452	653	
DDX54 - TIMELESS	697	1798	1747	DDX27 - TIMELESS	705	843	2279	
DDX51 - TIMELESS	963	2458	545	DDX20 - TIMELESS	1314	1715	756	
DDX55 - TIMELESS	1438	2115	746	DDX19A - TIMELESS	1566	436	1947	
DDX10 - TIMELESS	1721	2550	1540	DDX21 - TIMELESS	2141	187	1980	
DDX31 - TIMELESS	2217	2370	2295	DDX46 - TIMELESS	2453	1672	2495	
DDX56 - TIMELESS	2516	1615	2683					

Table 3: 2nd order interaction ranking between TIMELESS VS DDX members.

One can also interpret the results of the table 3 graphically, with the following influences - • DDX members w.r.t TIMELESS with TIMELESS → DDX-12P/28/18/11/27/51/20/55.

UNEXPLORED COMBINATORIAL HYPOTHESES

DDX members w.r.t TIMELESS

DDX-12P/28/18/11/27/51/20/55 TIMELESS

Table 4: 2nd order combinatorial hypotheses between TIMELESS and DDX members.

2.1.3. TIMELESS - POL/POLR

Cho et al. [6] show that mTIM and TIM-interacting protein (TIPIN) complex couple replicative DNA helicase CMG (CDC45, MCM2-7, GINS) and stimulate the activities of DNA polymerase (POL) α , δ , and ϵ , in progressing the replication fork. These experimental studies confirm the existence of synergy between the above involved factors with TIMELESS. In colorectal cancer cells treated with ETC-1922159, these POL members, and TIMELESS, were found to be down regulated and their regulation was recorded independently. I was able to rank 2nd order combination of these POL members along with TIMELESS. Additionally I ranked POLR (DNA-dependent RNA polymerase) also along with TIMELESS to see if there exists any synergy.

Table 5 shows rankings of these combinations. Followed by this is the unexplored combinatorial hypotheses in table 6 generated from analysis of the ranks in table 5. The table 5 shows rankings of POL/POLR members w.r.t TIMELESS. POLA1 - TIMELESS shows low ranking of 334 (laplace) and 145 (rbf). POLD1 - TIMELESS shows

low ranking of 399 (laplace) and 942 (rbf). POLE2 - TIMELESS shows low ranking of 479 (laplace) and 89 (rbf). POLE3 - TIMELESS shows low ranking of 1111 (laplace) and 1487 (rbf). POLG2 - TIMELESS shows low ranking of 1220 (laplace) and 1251 (rbf). POLR3K - TIMELESS shows low ranking of 96 (laplace) and 678 (rbf). POLR1A - TIMELESS shows low ranking of 515 (laplace), 737 (linear) and 1093 (rbf). POLR1E - TIMELESS shows low ranking of 820 (laplace) and 665 (rbf). POLR1B - TIMELESS shows low ranking of 1077 (laplace), 694 (linear) and 817 (rbf). POLR3E - TIMELESS shows low ranking of 1249 (laplace) and 1459 (linear). POLR2D - TIMELESS shows low ranking of 1264 (laplace) and 1106 (linear). POLR2G - TIMELESS shows low ranking of 1299 (laplace) and 1059 (rbf). POLR1C - TIMELESS shows low ranking of 1122 (linear) and 1313 (rbf). These rankings point to the synergy existing between the two components, which have been down regulated after the drug treatment.

Further, POLA2, POLD2, POLB, POLQ, POLR1D, POLR3A, POLR2K and POLR2F showed high ranking and might not be synergistically working with TIMELESS, before treatment.

RANKING POL MEMBERS VS TIMELESS								
RANKING OF POL MEMBERS W.R.T TIMELESS								
	laplace	linear	rbf		laplace	linear	rbf	
POLA1 - TIMELESS	334	2106	145	POLD1 - TIMELESS	399	2699	942	
POLE2 - TIMELESS	479	2206	89	POLE3 - TIMELESS	1111	2242	1487	
POLG2 - TIMELESS	1220	2197	1251	POLQ - TIMELESS	1561	617	2432	
POLA2 - TIMELESS	2454	83	1717	POLD2 - TIMELESS	2467	2216	1091	
POLB - TIMELESS	2706	1515	2585					
RANKING POLR MEMBERS VS TIMELESS								
RANKING OF POLR MEMBERS W.R.T TIMELESS								
	laplace	linear	rbf		laplace	linear	rbf	
POLR3K - TIMELESS	96	1591	678	POLR1A - TIMELESS	515	737	1093	
POLR1E - TIMELESS	820	2734	665	POLR1B - TIMELESS	1077	694	817	
POLR3E - TIMELESS	1249	1459	1715	POLR2D - TIMELESS	1264	1106	1932	
POLR2G - TIMELESS	1299	2486	1059	POLR1C - TIMELESS	1551	1122	1313	
POLR1D - TIMELESS	1692	1374	2448	POLR3A - TIMELESS	2405	1021	2534	
POLR2K - TIMELESS	2476	1567	2612	POLR2F - TIMELESS	2694	1632	2635	

Table 5: 2nd order interaction ranking between TIMELESS VS POL/POLR members.

One can also interpret the results of the table 5 graphically, with the following influences - • POL members w.r.t TIMELESS with TIMELESS – > POL-A1/D1/E2/E3/G2 and • POLR members w.r.t TIMELESS with TIMELESS – > POLR-3K/1A/1E/1B/3E/2D/2G/1C.

2.1.4. TIMELESS - MCM/GINS

Cho et al. [6] show that mTIM and TIM-interacting protein (TIPIN) complex couple replicative DNA helicase CMG (CDC45, MCM2-7, GINS) and stimulate the activities of DNA polymerase (POL) α , δ , and ϵ , in progressing the replication fork. These experimental studies confirm the existence of synergy between the above involved factors with TIMELESS. In colorectal cancer cells treated with ETC-1922159,

UNEXPLORED COMBINATORIAL HYPOTHESES	
POL members w.r.t TIMELESS	
POL-A1/D1/E2/E3/G2	TIMELESS
POLR members w.r.t TIMELESS	
POLR-3K/1A/1E/1B/3E/2D/2G/1C	TIMELESS

Table 6: 2nd order combinatorial hypotheses between TIMELESS and POL/POLR members.

these MCM/GINS members, and TIMELESS, were found to be down regulated and their regulation was recorded independently. I was able to rank 2nd order combination of these MCM/GINS members along with TIMELESS.

Table 7 shows rankings of these combinations. Followed by this is the unexplored combinatorial hypotheses in table 8 generated from analysis of the ranks in table 7. The table 7 shows rankings of MCM/GINS members w.r.t TIMELESS. MCM5 - TIMELESS shows low ranking of 147 (laplace), 770 (linear) and 926 (rbf). MCM3 - TIMELESS shows low ranking of 166 (laplace), 741 (linear) and 1033 (rbf). MCM2 - TIMELESS shows low ranking of 311 (laplace), 130 (linear) and 1438 (rbf). MCM4 - TIMELESS shows low ranking of 668 (laplace) and 305 (linear). MCMDC2 - TIMELESS shows low ranking of 718 (laplace), 1476 (linear) and 1508 (rbf). MCM8 - TIMELESS shows low ranking of 1085 (laplace), 13 (linear) and 1323 (rbf). MCM7 - TIMELESS shows low ranking of 1363 (laplace) and 461 (rbf). GINS4 - TIMELESS shows low ranking of 343 (laplace) and 186 (rbf). GINS1 - TIMELESS shows low ranking of 893 (laplace) and 865 (linear). GINS3 - TIMELESS shows low ranking of 939 (laplace), 401 (linear) and 274 (rbf). These rankings point to the synergy existing between the two components, which have been down regulated after the drug treatment.

Further, MCM6, MCM10 and GINS2 showed high ranking and might not be synergistically working with TIMELESS, before treatment.

One can also interpret the results of the table 7 graphically, with the following influences - • MCM members w.r.t TIMELESS with TIMELESS – > MCM-5/3/2/4/DC2/8/7 and • GINS members w.r.t TIMELESS with TIMELESS – > GINS-4/1/3.

2.1.5. TIMELESS - FBX/RNF/H2A

The mammalian FBXL10-RNF68-RNF2 ubiquitin ligase complex (FRRUC) mono-ubiquitylates H2A to repress transcription in unstressed cells. Rona et al. [21] found that the FRRUC was recruited to sites of DNA damage in a PARP1- and TIMELESS-dependent manner to promote mono-ubiquitylation of H2A, a local decrease of H2A levels, and an increase of H2A.Z incorporation. Both the FRRUC and H2A.Z promoted transcriptional repression, double strand break signaling, and homologous recombination repair (HRR). These experimental studies confirm the existence of synergy be-

RANKING MCM MEMBERS VS TIMELESS

RANKING OF MCM MEMBERS W.R.T TIMELESS			
	laplace	linear	rbf
MCM5 - TIMELESS	147	770	926
MCM3 - TIMELESS	166	741	1033
MCM2 - TIMELESS	311	130	1438
MCM4 - TIMELESS	668	305	1598
MCMDC2 - TIMELESS	718	1476	1508
MCM8 - TIMELESS	1085	13	1323
MCM7 - TIMELESS	1363	1839	461
MCM6 - TIMELESS	1570	2448	1404
MCM10 - TIMELESS	2636	1238	2008

RANKING GINS MEMBERS VS TIMELESS

RANKING OF GINS MEMBERS W.R.T TIMELESS			
	laplace	linear	rbf
GINS4 - TIMELESS	343	2088	186
GINS1 - TIMELESS	893	865	2160
GINS3 - TIMELESS	939	401	274
GINS2 - TIMELESS	2338	165	2699

Table 7: 2nd order interaction ranking between TIMELESS VS POL/POLR members.

UNEXPLORED COMBINATORIAL HYPOTHESES

MCM members w.r.t TIMELESS	
MCM-5/3/2/4/DC2/8/7	TIMELESS
GINS members w.r.t TIMELESS	
GINS-4/1/3	TIMELESS

Table 8: 2nd order combinatorial hypotheses between TIMELESS and POL/POLR members.

tween the above involved factors with TIMELESS. In colorectal cancer cells treated with ETC-1922159, these FBX-RNF-H2A members, and TIMELESS, were found to be down regulated and their regulation was recorded independently. I was able to rank 2nd order combination of these FBX-RNF-H2A members along with TIMELESS.

Table 9 shows rankings of these combinations. Followed by this is the unexplored combinatorial hypotheses in table 10 generated from analysis of the ranks in table 9. The table 9 shows rankings of FBX-RNF-H2A members w.r.t TIMELESS. FBXO5 - TIMELESS shows low ranking of 58 (laplace), 981 (linear) and 528 (rbf). FBXO4 - TIMELESS shows low ranking of 853 (laplace) and 1047 (rbf). FBXW9 - TIMELESS shows low ranking of 188 (linear) and 1142 (rbf). RNF20 - TIMELESS shows low ranking of 549 (laplace) and 984 (rbf). RNF166 - TIMELESS shows low ranking of 1147 (laplace) and 982 (rbf). RNF144B - TIMELESS shows low ranking of 1179 (laplace), 1437 (linear) and 1149 (rbf). H2AFV - TIMELESS shows low ranking of 332 (laplace), 1535 (linear) and 937 (rbf). H2AFX - TIMELESS shows low ranking of 401 (laplace), 1342 (linear) and 1065 (rbf). These rankings point to the synergy existing between the two components, which have been down regulated after the drug treatment.

Further, FBXL8, FBXO41, RNF220, RNF157, RNF43, RNF26 and H2AFZ showed high ranking and might not be synergistically working with TIMELESS, before treatment.

One can also interpret the results of the table 9 graphically, with the following influences - ● FBX members w.r.t TIMELESS with TIMELESS – > FBX-O5/O4/W9; ● RNF members w.r.t TIMELESS with TIMELESS – > RNF-20/166/144B and ● H2A members w.r.t TIMELESS with TIMELESS – > H2A-FV/FX.

2.1.6. TIMELESS - HMG/WNT

Wang et al. [22] showed by functional studies that TIM knockdown reduced endometrial cancer (EC) cell viability and restrained EC cell migration in vitro, as well as blocked xenograft tumor growth in vivo. Mechanistically, HMGB1 transcriptionally up-regulated TIM expression which led to activation of transcription of the WNT8B. On the other hand depletion of TIM decreased the malignant potential of EC cells by targeting and down-regulating WNT8B. These experimental studies confirm the existence of synergy between the above involved factors with TIMELESS. In colorectal cancer cells treated with ETC-1922159, these HMG members, and TIMELESS, were found to be down regulated and their regulation was recorded independently. I was able to rank 2nd order combination of these HMG members along with TIMELESS.

Table 11 shows rankings of these combinations. Followed by this is the unexplored combinatorial hypotheses in table 12 generated from analysis of the ranks in table 11. The table 11 shows rankings of HMG-RNF-H2A members w.r.t TIMELESS. HMGN5 - TIMELESS shows low ranking of 169 (laplace) and 433 (rbf). HMGB3 - TIMELESS shows low ranking of 755 (laplace) and 1126 (rbf). HMGN2 - TIMELESS shows low ranking of 990 (laplace) and 346 (rbf). HMGB2 - TIMELESS shows low ranking of 1487 (laplace) and 1419 (linear). HMGB1 - TIMELESS shows low ranking of 677 (linear) and 1466 (rbf). WNT10B - TIMELESS shows low ranking of 266 (laplace) and 35 (rbf). These rankings point to the synergy existing between the two components,

RANKING FBX MEMBERS VS TIMELESS			
RANKING OF FBX MEMBERS W.R.T TIMELESS			
	laplace	linear	rbf
FBXO5 - TIMELESS	58	981	528
FBXO4 - TIMELESS	853	1850	1047
FBXL8 - TIMELESS	2100	2190	1557
FBXO41 - TIMELESS	2415	1479	1941
FBXW9 - TIMELESS	2579	188	1142

RANKING RNF MEMBERS VS TIMELESS			
RANKING OF RNF MEMBERS W.R.T TIMELESS			
	laplace	linear	rbf
RNF20 - TIMELESS	549	2001	984
RNF220 - TIMELESS	930	1603	2410
RNF166 - TIMELESS	1147	2511	982
RNF144B - TIMELESS	1179	1437	1149
RNF157 - TIMELESS	2257	1837	1237
RNF43 - TIMELESS	2556	1433	1699
RNF26 - TIMELESS	2711	2336	2330

RANKING H2A MEMBERS VS TIMELESS			
RANKING OF H2A MEMBERS W.R.T TIMELESS			
	laplace	linear	rbf
H2AFV - TIMELESS	332	1535	937
H2AFX - TIMELESS	401	1342	1065
H2AFZ - TIMELESS	2421	2622	1434

Table 9: 2nd order interaction ranking between TIMELESS VS FBX members.

which have been down regulated after the drug treatment.

One can also interpret the results of the table 11 graphically, with the following influences - • HMG members w.r.t TIMELESS with TIMELESS - > HMG-N5/B3/N2/B2/B1 and • WNT members w.r.t TIMELESS with TIMELESS - > WNT10B.

UNEXPLORED COMBINATORIAL HYPOTHESES	
FBX members w.r.t TIMELESS	
FBX-O5/O4/W9	TIMELESS
RNF members w.r.t TIMELESS	
RNF-20/166/144B	TIMELESS
H2A members w.r.t TIMELESS	
H2A-FV/FX	TIMELESS

Table 10: 2^{nd} order combinatorial hypotheses between TIMELESS and FBX members.

RANKING HMG-WNT MEMBERS VS TIMELESS			
RANKING OF HMG-WNT MEMBERS W.R.T TIMELESS			
	laplace	linear	rbf
HMGN5 - TIMELESS	169	2524	433
HMGB3 - TIMELESS	755	2232	1126
HMGN2 - TIMELESS	990	2593	346
HMGB2 - TIMELESS	1487	1419	1874
HMGB1 - TIMELESS	2496	677	1466
WNT10B - TIMELESS	266	1630	35

Table 11: 2^{nd} order interaction ranking between TIMELESS VS HMG members.

UNEXPLORED COMBINATORIAL HYPOTHESES	
HMG members w.r.t TIMELESS	
HMG-N5/B3/N2/B2/B1	TIMELESS
WNT members w.r.t TIMELESS	
WNT10B	TIMELESS

Table 12: 2^{nd} order combinatorial hypotheses between TIMELESS and HMG members.

2.1.7. TIMELESS - MIR(x)HG/FOX

In breast cancer stem cells, Zou et al. [23] observed that c-Jun enhanced MIR-5188 transcription to form a positive regulatory loop, and TIMELESS interacted with Sp1/c-Jun to induce MIR-5188 expression by promoting c-Jun-mediated transcription, which further activated MIR-5188-FOXO1/ β -catenin-c-Jun loop and facilitated breast cancer progression. These experimental studies confirm the existence of synergy between the above involved factors with TIMELESS. In colorectal cancer cells treated with ETC-1922159, these MIR-FOX members, and TIMELESS, were found to be down regulated and their regulation was recorded independently. I was able to rank 2nd order combination of these MIR-FOX members along with TIMELESS.

Table 13 shows rankings of these combinations. Followed by this is the unexplored combinatorial hypotheses in table 14 generated from analysis of the ranks in table 13. The table 13 shows rankings of MIR-FOX members w.r.t TIMELESS. MIR17HG - TIMELESS shows low ranking of 514 (linear) and 1086 (rbf). FOXJ1 - TIMELESS shows low ranking of 771 (laplace), 726 (linear) and 95 (rbf). FOXA2 - TIMELESS shows low ranking of 1387 (laplace), 1447 (linear) and 509 (rbf). These rankings point to the synergy existing between the two components, which have been down regulated after the drug treatment.

Further, MIR155HG and FOXM1 showed high ranking and might not be synergistically working with TIMELESS, before treatment.

RANKING MIR-FOX MEMBERS VS TIMELESS			
RANKING OF MIR-FOX MEMBERS W.R.T TIMELESS			
	laplace	linear	rbf
MIR155HG - TIMELESS	1793	1791	700
MIR17HG - TIMELESS	2133	514	1086
FOXJ1 - TIMELESS	771	726	95
FOXA2 - TIMELESS	1387	1447	509
FOXM1 - TIMELESS	2154	328	2364

Table 13: 2nd order interaction ranking between TIMELESS VS MIR-FOX members.

One can also interpret the results of the table 13 graphically, with the following influences - ● MIR members w.r.t TIMELESS with TIMELESS – > MIR17HG and ● FOX members w.r.t TIMELESS with TIMELESS – > FOX-J1/A2.

2.1.8. TIMELESS - PARP

TIMELESS in the fork protection complex acts as a scaffold of the replisome to prevent its uncoupling and ensure efficient DNA replication fork progression. Saldanha et al. [24] demonstrated that acute degradation of TIMELESS at ongoing DNA replication forks induced the accumulation of ssDNA gaps stemming from defective Okazaki

UNEXPLORED COMBINATORIAL HYPOTHESES	
MIR members w.r.t TIMELESS	
MIR17HG	TIMELESS
FOX members w.r.t TIMELESS	
FOX-J1/A2	TIMELESS

Table 14: 2nd order combinatorial hypotheses between TIMELESS and MIR-FOX members.

fragment (OF) processing. Cells lacking TIMELESS failed to support the poly(ADP-ribose)ylation necessary for backing up the canonical OF processing mechanism mediated by LIG1 and FEN1. Physical disruption of the TIMELESSPARP1 complex phenocopies the rapid loss of TIM, indicating that the TIMELESSPARP1 interaction is critical for the activation of this pathway. Accordingly, combined deficiency of FEN1 and the TIMELESSPARP1 interaction led to synergistic DNA damage and cytotoxicity. These experimental studies confirm the existence of synergy between the above involved factors with TIMELESS. In colorectal cancer cells treated with ETC-1922159, these PARP members, and TIMELESS, were found to be down regulated and their regulation was recorded independently. I was able to rank 2nd order combination of these PARP members along with TIMELESS.

Table 15 shows rankings of these combinations. Followed by this is the unexplored combinatorial hypotheses in table 16 generated from analysis of the ranks in table 15. The table 15 shows rankings of MIR-PARP members w.r.t TIMELESS. PARP1 - TIMELESS shows low ranking of 828 (linear) and 796 (rbf). PARP2 - TIMELESS shows low ranking of 1241 (linear) and 801 (rbf). These rankings point to the synergy existing between the two components, which have been down regulated after the drug treatment.

Further, PARPBP and PARP16 showed high ranking and might not be synergistically working with TIMELESS, before treatment.

One can also interpret the results of the table 15 graphically, with the following influences - • PARP members w.r.t TIMELESS with TIMELESS – > PARP-1/2.

2.1.9. TIMELESS - PDE

Barrio-Alonso et al. [25] identified TIMELESS targeting synaptic-plasticity-related genes such as PDE4B. By promoting PDE4B transcription, TIMELESS negatively regulated cAMP signaling to modulate AMPA receptor GLUA1 function and influence synaptic plasticity. These experimental studies confirm the existence of synergy between the above involved factors with TIMELESS. In colorectal cancer cells treated with ETC-1922159, these PDE members, and TIMELESS, were found to be down regulated and their regulation was recorded independently. I was able to rank 2nd order combination of these PDE members along with TIMELESS.

RANKING PARP MEMBERS VS TIMELESS			
RANKING OF PARP MEMBERS W.R.T TIMELESS			
	laplace	linear	rbf
PARP1 - TIMELESS	1582	828	796
PARP2 - TIMELESS	1685	1241	801
PARPBP - TIMELESS	1895	2742	1788
PARP16 - TIMELESS	2716	1886	2716

Table 15: 2nd order interaction ranking between TIMELESS VS PARP members.

UNEXPLORED COMBINATORIAL HYPOTHESES	
PARP members w.r.t TIMELESS	
PARP-1/2	TIMELESS

Table 16: 2nd order combinatorial hypotheses between TIMELESS and PARP members.

Table 17 shows rankings of these combinations. Followed by this is the unexplored combinatorial hypotheses in table 18 generated from analysis of the ranks in table 17. The table 17 shows rankings of MIR-PDE members w.r.t TIMELESS. PDE7A - TIMELESS shows low ranking of 1189 (laplace) and 1038 (rbf). These rankings point to the synergy existing between the two components, which have been down regulated after the drug treatment.

Further, PDE4DIP showed high ranking and might not be synergistically working with TIMELESS, before treatment.

RANKING PDE MEMBERS VS TIMELESS			
RANKING OF PDE MEMBERS W.R.T TIMELESS			
	laplace	linear	rbf
PDE7A - TIMELESS	1189	2614	1038
PDE4DIP - TIMELESS	2082	1997	1757

Table 17: 2nd order interaction ranking between TIMELESS VS PDE members.

One can also interpret the results of the table 17 graphically, with the following influences - • PDE members w.r.t TIMELESS with TIMELESS – > PDE-7A.

UNEXPLORED COMBINATORIAL HYPOTHESES

PDE members w.r.t TIMELESS

PDE-7A	TIMELESS
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Table 18: 2nd order combinatorial hypotheses between TIMELESS and PDE members.

3. Conclusion

Presented here are a range of multiple synergistic TIMELESS 2nd order combinations that were ranked via a machine learning based search engine. Via majority voting across the ranking methods, it was possible to find plausible unexplored synergistic combinations of TIMELESS-X that might be prevalent in CRC cells after treatment with ETC-1922159 drug.

Conflict of interest

There are no conflicts to declare.

Author's contributions

Concept, design, in silico implementation - SS. Analysis and interpretation of results - SS. Manuscript writing - SS. Manuscript revision - SS. Approval of manuscript - SS

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Source of Data

Data used in this research work was released in a publication in Madan et al. [26].

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